

**THE ROLE OF THE TEACHER IN ORGANIZING AND COMPLETING TRIPS IN SPORTS
TOURISM**

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Annotation: *This article focuses on the role of the teacher in guiding students in the right direction in organizing trips in sports tourism.*

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The role of the pedagogical team in the development of tourism activities in schools, academic lyceums, and higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan is of great importance. In addition to educational activities, students are now closely assisted in extracurricular activities, career choices, sports and travel. Teachers of geography, botany, history, and physical education are primarily active in attracting students to tourism and local history groups, organizing and conducting trips. During trips, the mood of both the teacher and the students is not always good. Sometimes various arguments, disputes, resentments, even complaints arise. In order to prevent this situation, the tour leader finds the culprits, blames them, and reprimands them in front of many people. As a result, the tourist community fully restores its unity on the way to the common goal. The trip is voluntary.

The following requirements and duties are imposed and the rights are given when becoming a travel guide:

1. Organization of the group and taking full responsibility for it.
2. To be a highly qualified person who participated in or led mountain tourism trips (high category III-IV).
3. Rights of tour leaders:
 - a) to take action against those who violate the travel rules, to exclude them from the group;
 - b) change the routes if necessary;
 - c) handing over one's group to a more experienced instructor or specialist when circumstances require;

The leader is obliged to:

- a) prepare tourists for travel at an appropriate level;
- b) introduction of travel routes, social and useful works, plans for exploration and study of the country;
- c) drawing up a map or scheme, ensuring safety on the road;

- g) to study the obstacles on the road, if necessary, to choose and designate alternative routes;
- d) introducing hydrometeorological changes;
- e) preparation of relevant equipment in advance, travel expenses, calculation and collection of food;
- j) keeping the route book and submitting it to the route qualification commission (MKK);
- z) obtaining a permit and relevant advice from weather, geology, forestry and other agencies on the road;
- i) regular monitoring of the order and discipline of the group;
- y) inspection of road safety maintenance and rescue control agencies;
- k) marking the route book in certain places;
- l) reporting to rescue checkpoints passed during the trip;
- m) quickly deliver the injured to the appropriate places; n) quickly notify when an accident occurs;

Only the most experienced tourist and teacher can perform such important duties. Therefore, the teacher is considered the main force in conducting the trip. The tour leader will make a written report for the whole trip. It shows the routes passed and the main works done. The route sheet and photos are attached to the report or wall newspaper

As mentioned in the previous topics, students can get sick, fall and be injured during trips. In such cases, it is necessary for tourists to know the procedures and rules of providing first aid, and to apply it in practice. As a result of the carelessness of tourists, they can get burned in the campfire, while cooking. In order to prevent such incidents from happening, the duty officers (cooks, tea makers, and porters) must always be fully dressed and have special equipment in their hands. In general, when it burns, it is necessary to extinguish it quickly. For this, it is necessary to quickly remove clothes, soak in water and rub with soil or sand. If you get a burn, it is recommended to put it in cold water for 10-15 minutes. After that, it is necessary to moisten the gauze and rub it with alcohol or manganese. In the case of 1st-2nd degree burns, it is necessary to lubricate the skin with sulfidine emulsion, to consult a doctor when coming to a village or residential area. At nighttime, sharp objects (axes, knives, stakes, stones, etc.) are struck and injured. In such cases, it is possible to wash the injured area, apply iodine, sprinkle streptocide powder on it and cover the wound with a plaster.

In case of non-stop bleeding as a result of an injury, the blood vessel (artery) should be firmly pressed. When bleeding does not subside, it is necessary to tightly bandage the upper part of the wound. The injured area can be bandaged for 1-2 hours. It is necessary to loosen it for 3-4 minutes without stopping the bleeding, and then tie it tightly again. When oskozon is poisoned, it is necessary to wash it, that is, add soda to several glasses of warm water, and continue until it is thrown away, repeating this situation several times. Then it is necessary to strictly follow the diet. As a result of long walks, heavy loads and falls, the

body can be scratched, scratched and bruised. These cases are more common in the legs, shoulders and back. In such cases, it is enough to quickly prevent it and apply baby cream. As a result of falls, the flesh of the legs and arms can be crushed and bruised. In such cases, it is necessary to apply iodine to the affected area, compress with cold water or (ice). After that, it is recommended to tie it tighter. Stretching and crushing of the joints is felt with severe pain. Then the area may become swollen and painful when moved. In such cases, a bandage soaked in cold water (pressing with a material, then it is necessary to tie it with an elastic bandage or something that can replace it). , it becomes impossible to move. In such cases, it is necessary to hold the arm and leg in order to put them in place. After the joints are in place, it is necessary to tie them with a splint In case of broken bones of the arm and leg, it is necessary to bind them with splints, to give pain relievers and to send them to the doctor immediately. In such cases, the patient should be placed lower than the head.

Hands, feet, ears, or face can get frostbite in the icy zones of winter frosts or summer frosts. In such cases, rubbing, moving quickly, performing various gymnastic exercises, and when you lose the ability to walk, rolling (massage) with some material (blanket, blanket, etc.), and if this does not help, wipe with alcohol. will be needed. Drinking hot tea, taking a few glucose tablets with vitamin C is very beneficial. If blisters appear in the affected area, penicillin ointment or syntomycin emulsion is applied and applied. The patient should be given tetracycline, if the condition worsens, analgin, amidopyrine, caffeine and the patient should be taken to the medical center. It is enough to wear appropriate clothes and glasses and use them at the right time in order to avoid sunlight. Tourists who are not used to hot weather should not go half-naked or naked and lie down in the heat when their stomachs are hungry. Sunbathing should be done only gradually. The lamb is quickly damaged by the shine of the snow and the reflected light. That is why it is forbidden to walk in snowy areas without a mirror to always look at one point. In such cases, the affected eye is washed with a small amount of boric acid mixture, sodas, potassium permanganate, and potassium solution, and tea, and the tourist is freed from walking for several days. It is not good to spread wild fruits without washing them, to grab and smell every flower and tree. Dishes containing mushrooms, fungus and other spreading things should also be washed. In the mountain and desert zones, rabid wild boar or wolves may be encountered. If they attack a person, they pinch their ears and snarl and retreat. In such cases, tourists should be in pairs and have sticks and weapons ready. There will be a danger of poisonous snakes in the mountain and desert zone. When you see a snake, you should not touch it or kill it. The reason for this is that venomous snakes are primarily needed for medicine. Recently, measures to breed poisonous snakes have been observed. As a result of carelessness, tourists may not be afraid of a snake lying among the grasses, kings, and bushes and run over it. Because of this, the snakes, full of anger, tried to bite. He will take revenge. If you suddenly see a snake while you are resting or sitting, and it does not run away, you should carry it away with a stick or a stick. If a snake bite is quickly felt, the first thing to do is to suck the place. It is necessary to quickly spit out the poison mixed with blood. If there is a

sore in the mouth, someone else should suck it. The upper part of the bitten area should be clamped tightly, bandaged, and a doctor should be consulted immediately. In first aid, it is recommended to give the patient liquid and warmer drink and food. Because the poison mixes with liquids and reduces its strength. Poison can be excreted through urine and digestive tract. According to experience, it is impossible to over-tighten (especially with a tourniquet) the place of a snake bite. Because the poison does not spread through blood vessels, but through lymphatic fluids. Also, burning or cutting off the bite does not give the expected result. Because the injured snakebite can quickly get into a serious condition as a result of wounding and suppuration. Cutting the bite is very dangerous. As a result of not being able to stop the bleeding, the patient may end up in a serious condition. It should be remembered that poison thins the blood.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Xusanbayev B.M., Tulaganov L.A., Razina V.G., Dorogami Velikogo shelkovogo puti, T., 1995 y
2. Kolbinsev A.V., V gorax Chimgana, T., "O'zbekiston", 1984 y
3. Rasek V., Puteshestviye po Ferganskoy doline, T., 1978 yJismoniy tarbiya va sport mavzusidagi Respublika va Xalqaro ilmiy anjumanlarning to'plamlari, 1991-2006 yy.
4. www.referat.uz
5. www.ZiyoNET